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Eddy currents damping understood as Zener viscoelastic damping

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Abstract

This paper identifies and explains the eddy currents damping originated in a solid that vibrates in a magnetic field as a Zener viscoelastic model damping. For that, a coupled mechanical-electrical model is proposed for the eddy currents damping. The mechanical model is studied as a single degree-of-freedom system, and the electrical model is assumed to be a closed RL circuit. The coupling between them is given by the magnetic force originated by the motional inductance. The motion equation is obtained for the coupled system for two different excitation types: harmonic force and harmonic base motion. These motion equations include derivatives of the displacement with respect to time up to the third order. An equivalence between these motion equations and the ones derived for a viscoelastic system modelled with a Zener model is found. This allows understanding the parameters of the eddy currents model as the ones of a viscoelastic Zener model. The term related with the third order derivative is associated with relaxation, a characteristic property of viscoelastic systems. This equivalence between Zener and eddy currents damping explains forces proportional to the third order derivative that other authors have experimentally found in vibrating systems with eddy currents. The proposed model is validated both from an analytical comparison with another model of the literature and from experimental results previously published. Finally, a parametric study is carried out to show up the influence of the magnetic field and electrical properties of the model on the frequency and time responses of the system.

Keywords: eddy currents, Zener viscoelastic model, relaxation time; self-inductance

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 When a non-magnetic and metallic conductor moves in an external magnetic field, Foucault
37 currents appear, also known as eddy currents. These eddy currents, which have been studied
38 since the nineteenth century, can be a problem for the correct working of many systems,
39 going from transformers [1] to vacuum chambers in synchrotrons [2]. But, at the same time,
40 eddy currents can be very useful in many different applications. For example, they provide
41 non-destructive probing tests to find cracks in metal plates [3], and levitation melting uses
42 eddy currents to avoid the contamination of containers with certain particles [4,5]. Also,
43 many authors have proposed the use of eddy currents to act on dynamical systems, such as
44 magnetic breaks [6,7], dampers for seismic excitations [8], and lever-type vibration isolators
45 [9]. Some studies such as [10] and [11] presented a thorough review of these varied
46 applications.

47 Non-contact passive electromagnetic dampers have been used since a long time ago.
48 The main advantage of using the phenomenon of eddy currents to attenuate structural
49 vibration is the possibility of removing energy from the system without contact with the
50 structure itself [10]. Studies focusing on this non-contact feature have shown that the natural
51 frequencies of the structure are not changed in such cases [12,13]. In addition, unlike other
52 damping techniques, such as viscoelastic materials or piezoelectric actuators, no mass is
53 added to the structure to be damped. Most of the works that analyse the eddy currents
54 phenomenon have focused on designing eddy currents devices that significantly magnify the
55 damping added to the structure, but resulting also in a significant modification of the original
56 structural properties [10–13].

57 The modelling and analysis of eddy currents and their induced damping have been
58 tackled from several angles in the last decades, given the great importance of these
59 electromagnetic-mechanical coupling for many engineering devices [14,15]. For all its
60 practical applications, the mathematical theory and models behind eddy currents induction
61 are notoriously complex. There is a lack of simple models and methods capable of describing
62 the influence of eddy currents induced by different magnetic field configurations. Recently
63 Loong et. al [16] have modelled the forces involved in the damping from the eddy currents
64 as a Kelvin-Voigt model in a magneto-quasistatic approximation, and these forces have also
65 been studied with a fractional Kelvin-Voigt model in parallel acting on an equivalent *RL*
circuit [17], for instance. In any case, it has been shown that both the self-inductance and the

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67 jerk (the derivative of the acceleration) are crucial in order to fit any of these results to
68 experimental data.

69 From this background, this work presents the eddy currents damping effect
70 understood as a Zener viscoelastic model, therefore showing an equivalence between the
71 mechanical and the electromagnetic areas of research. This viscoelastic model is simple and
72 well known in the field of rheology, which helps to interpret the effects of the currents in the
73 system as well as to identify the self-inductance as a mechanical relaxation of the system. In
74 the mechanical-electrical model proposed in this paper, it can be found that the third order
75 derivative of the displacement obtained is equivalent to that found in a Zener viscoelastic
76 model. This third order derivative describes the relaxation of the system. Considering that
77 the relaxation from the electrical part is associated to the self-inductance, and applying these
78 ideas to a system subjected to eddy currents, it is shown a perfect match between the damping
79 coming from eddy currents and that which is characteristic to a Zener viscoelastic model.
80 Besides these advantages associated to the model, it also explains the experimental results
81 obtained by [16,18] and agrees with previous analytical results [17]. Also, the present work
82 could make the engineering problem of the design of eddy currents dampers easier, due to
83 the correlation of these systems with the well-known Zener viscoelastic model.

84 In short, in this paper, a theoretical background on Zener viscoelastic model is
85 presented. Next, a coupled mechanical-electrical model for the eddy currents is proposed for
86 two different types of excitations, namely, harmonic force and harmonic base motion, and
87 the equivalence with the Zener viscoelastic model is analysed. Then, a validation of the
88 model is presented, both with an analytical comparison with another model of other authors
89 [17], and with experimental results previously published [18]. Finally, a parametric study is
90 performed to reveal the influence of some parameters on the response of the system. On the
91 one hand, the influence of the magnetic field strength on the frequency transmissibility
92 function is studied. And on the other hand, it has been analysed the influence of the electrical
93 properties on the time response, relating them with the damping factors of the equivalent
94 Zener model.

95 96 **2. Brief background on Zener viscoelastic model**

97 The Zener model, also known as the Standard Linear Solid (SLS) model, is a method to
98 model the behaviour of viscoelastic materials by means of a linear combination of two
99 springs and a dashpot. This is the simplest model able to reproduce creep and relaxation,

100 both phenomena being characteristics of the viscoelastic behaviour. Therefore, this model is
 101 said to have memory, *i.e.*, the current response is a result of the complete history of the
 102 system.

103 In this Section, the governing equations of a vibrating single degree-of-freedom
 104 (DOF) system with Zener damping are presented for two different excitation types. The first
 105 case is a system excited by a force, and the second one is a system subjected to a base motion.
 106 These two cases are employed for the analogy with eddy currents damping in Section 3 and
 107 in the validation of Section 4.

108
 109 *2.1. Case 1: forced response*

110 Figure 1 represents a forced single degree-of-freedom system in which the viscoelasticity
 111 has been modelled by means of a Zener model. The external force is $f(t)$, the mass of the
 112 system is m , the stiffness of the in-parallel spring is k_0 , and the stiffness and viscous
 113 coefficient of the in-series spring and dashpot are k_1 and c , respectively. The motion
 114 equation for the displacement $u(t)$ is given by

$$115 \quad m\ddot{u}(t) + c(\dot{u}(t) - \dot{y}(t)) + k_0 u(t) = f(t), \quad (1)$$

116 where $y(t)$ is an internal variable that represents the displacement of the connecting point
 117 between the in-series spring and the dashpot. The force equilibrium in this point implies that

$$118 \quad k_1 y(t) = c(\dot{u}(t) - \dot{y}(t)). \quad (2)$$

119
 120 Fig. 1. Representation of the Zener model in a forced single degree-of-freedom system.

121
 122 This set of two differential equations with two unknowns, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$, can be solved by
 123 different ways. García-Barruetaña et al. [19] discussed on two different methods, one
 124 solving the internal variable $y(t)$ and the other one without solving the internal variable.

125 The latter consists in the transformation of Eq. (1) and (2) in linear algebraic equations by
 126 operational calculus, yielding

$$127 \quad \left[\frac{c}{k_1} m s^3 + m s^2 + \frac{c}{k_1} (k_0 + k_1) s + k_0 \right] U(s) = \left(\frac{c}{k_1} s + 1 \right) F(s), \quad (3)$$

128 where $U(s)$ and $F(s)$ are the Laplace transforms of $u(t)$ and of $f(t)$, respectively. By
 129 means of the inverse transform, the corresponding third order differential equation results in

$$130 \quad \tau m \ddot{u}(t) + m \dot{u}(t) + \tau (k_0 + k_1) \dot{u}(t) + k_0 u(t) = \tau \dot{f}(t) + f(t), \quad (4)$$

131 where τ is defined as the relaxation time of the system, which is given by

$$132 \quad \tau = \frac{c}{k_1}. \quad (5)$$

133 A force proportional to the derivative of the acceleration $\ddot{u}(t)$ (known as jerk) appears in
 134 Eq. (4). This force is what provides relaxation into the system, *i.e.*, it is zero when the
 135 relaxation time τ is zero, and in that case the system behaves as a viscous one, without
 136 relaxation.

137 2.2. Case 2: base motion

138 In this second case, the single degree-of-freedom system of the previous case is subjected to
 139 a base displacement $z(t)$ instead to a force, as represented in Fig. 2.

141 Fig. 2. Representation of the Zener model in a single degree-of-freedom system with base motion.

142 Here the motion equation is given by

$$143 \quad m \ddot{u}(t) + c (\dot{u}(t) - \dot{y}(t)) + k_0 (u(t) - z(t)) = 0, \quad (6)$$

144 and the equation of the force equilibrium at the connection point of the model is

$$145 \quad k_1 (y(t) - z(t)) = c (\dot{u}(t) - \dot{y}(t)). \quad (7)$$

148 Making use of the operational calculus in an equivalent way to that in Case 1, the resulting
149 equation yields

$$150 \quad \tau m \ddot{u}(t) + m \ddot{u}(t) + \tau(k_0 + k_1) \dot{u}(t) + k_0 u(t) = \tau(k_0 + k_1) \dot{z}(t) + k_0 z(t), \quad (8)$$

151 where the right-hand term of the equation represents the force that must be applied to the
152 base to obtain the desired movement.

153

154 **3. Eddy currents damping model and analogy with Zener**

155 Let us consider a metallic solid that vibrates in a uniform magnetic field. Eddy currents
156 appear in this solid due to the motional inductance, which implies Joule's losses that
157 dissipate mechanical energy to heat. From the mechanical point of view, this energy
158 dissipation is due to the magnetic force that appears by the interaction between the induced
159 eddy currents and the imposed magnetic field. Therefore, the vibration is attenuated by the
160 eddy currents, and these effects can be named as eddy currents damping.

161 In order to present an analogy between the eddy currents damping and a Zener
162 viscoelastic damping, in this section the motion of a metallic bar vibrating in a uniform time-
163 invariant magnetic field is modelled as a single degree-of-freedom system. Two different
164 cases are studied: first the case of the bar subjected to an external force $f(t)$, and next the
165 case of the base motion.

166

167 *3.1. Case 1: forced response*

168 Figure 3 represents the bar attached to a set of springs of global stiffness k_0 . The mass of the
169 bar is m and its length is ℓ . The bar slides without friction over metallic rails, conforming a
170 closed electrical line, whose contour is C . The bar moves in the x direction, the displacement
171 being $\mathbf{u}(t) = u(t) \mathbf{x}$. The governing equation of the motion of the bar is given by

$$172 \quad m \ddot{u}(t) + k_0 u(t) = f_m(t) + f(t), \quad (9)$$

173 where the external forces are separated into the contribution of the magnetic force $f_m(t)$ and
174 that of the rest of the external forces $f(t)$. The magnetic force experienced by the metallic
175 bar is determined next.

Fig. 3. Representation of a forced single degree-of-freedom system moving in a uniform and time-invariant magnetic field, in which an induced current in an equivalent RL circuit appears.

The magnetic field is uniform and constant in the z direction, represented by the magnetic intensity $\mathbf{B} = B \mathbf{z}$. An electromotive force $\mathcal{E}_{\text{ind}}$ is induced by motional inductance, known as motional EMF (see any textbook on the field, for instance [20]), given by

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ind}} = \oint_C (\dot{\mathbf{u}} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot d\mathbf{l}, \quad (10)$$

where the integral along the closed contour C results in

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ind}}(t) = \dot{u}(t) B \ell. \quad (11)$$

This motional EMF induces a current $i(t)$ in the line, in which the resistance R and the inductance L are actually the resistance and the self-inductance of the metallic solid in which the eddy currents appear. The equation that governs the circuit is

$$L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + R i(t) = \mathcal{E}_{\text{ind}}(i), \quad (12)$$

wherefrom the magnetoelectrical and mechanical coupling results in

$$L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + R i(t) = \dot{u}(t) B \ell. \quad (13)$$

The magnetoelectrical-mechanical coupling is also given by the magnetic force $f_m(t)$ acting of the bar, that according to Lorentz law, is given by

$$\mathbf{f}_m(t) = i(t) \mathbf{l} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{l} = -\ell \mathbf{y}$. Thus, the magnetic force yields

$$f_m(t) = -i(t) B \ell, \quad (15)$$

197 where the negative sign implies that the sense of this force is the opposite to that represented
 198 in Fig. 3.

199 Summarizing, a set of three differential equations is reached, given by Eqs. (9), (13)
 200 and (15), the three unknowns being the displacement $u(t)$, the current intensity $i(t)$ and the
 201 magnetic force $f_m(t)$. This may be transformed into an algebraic linear system by means of
 202 operational calculus, resulting in

$$203 \quad (s^2 m + k_0)U(s) = F_m(s) + F(s), \quad (16)$$

$$204 \quad (sL + R)I(s) = sU(s)B\ell \quad (17)$$

205 and

$$206 \quad F_m(s) = -I(s)B\ell, \quad (18)$$

207 where $U(s)$, $I(s)$, $F_m(s)$ and $F(s)$ are the Laplace transform of $u(t)$, $i(t)$, $f_m(t)$ and $f(t)$

208 . As a result, the next equation is obtained for the displacement,

$$209 \quad \left[\frac{L}{R} m s^3 + m s^2 + \frac{L}{R} \left(k_0 + \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{L} \right) s + k_0 \right] U(s) = \left(\frac{L}{R} s + 1 \right) F(s), \quad (19)$$

210 whose differential equation yields

$$211 \quad \frac{L}{R} m \ddot{u}(t) + m \ddot{u}(t) + \frac{L}{R} \left(k_0 + \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{L} \right) \dot{u}(t) + k_0 u(t) = \frac{L}{R} \dot{f}(t) + f(t). \quad (20)$$

212 On one hand, it can be pointed out that this differential equation is the same as that of the
 213 Zener model given by the Eq. (4). In this context, the equivalent stiffness k_1 is given by

$$214 \quad k_1 = \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{L}, \quad (21)$$

215 the equivalent viscous coefficient c of the dashpot is given by

$$216 \quad c = \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{R}, \quad (22)$$

217 and, consequently, the equivalent relaxation time τ is

$$218 \quad \tau = \frac{L}{R}, \quad (23)$$

219 which beautifully coincides with the time constant of a RL circuit. It also should be noted
 220 that, if the self-inductance of the bar is negligible, the Zener model derives in the Kelvin-
 221 Voigt model, resulting

$$222 \quad m\ddot{u}(t) + \frac{B^2\ell^2}{R}\dot{u}(t) + k_0u(t) = f(t), \quad (24)$$

223 that is, the dissipative forces derived by the eddy currents would be purely viscous. Hence,
 224 the self-inductance is the property allowing the relaxation of the system, a characteristic of
 225 viscoelastic systems described by a Zener model, as opposed to the viscous behaviour
 226 described by a Kelvin-Voigt model. Indeed, as Eq. (23) shows, a zero self-inductance implies
 227 no relaxation.

228
 229 On the other hand, according to Eq. (20), it can be noted that the eddy currents damping
 230 involves forces proportional to the first and third derivatives of the displacement with respect
 231 to time. Hence, this model justifies two of the three kinds of forces that [16] proposed to be
 232 fitted to experimental results. However, Eq. (20) does not explain forces related to the
 233 acceleration. This is because eddy currents do not imply inertial forces since they have a
 234 dissipative nature.

235
 236 Finally, as for the internal variable $y(t)$ of the Zener model described in Section 2, this eddy
 237 currents model yields

$$238 \quad \frac{B^2\ell^2}{L}y(t) = \frac{B^2\ell^2}{R}(\dot{u}(t) - \dot{y}(t)), \quad (25)$$

239 that is,

$$240 \quad L\dot{y}(t) + Ry(t) = L\dot{u}(t). \quad (26)$$

241 This last equation is the same as equation (13) if the internal variable $y(t)$ is defined as

$$242 \quad y(t) = \frac{L}{B} \frac{i(t)}{\ell}. \quad (27)$$

243 Thus, in the Zener model equivalent to eddy currents damping, the internal variable is
 244 proportionally related to the current intensity linear density $i(t)/\ell$. If the last equation is
 245 written as

$$246 \quad Li(t) = B\ell y(t), \quad (28)$$

247 the left-hand side represents the magnetic flux generated by the induced current, and the
 248 right-hand side represents the flux of the impressed magnetic field of intensity B , over an
 249 area $\ell y(t)$.

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251 3.2. Case 2: base motion

252 In this second case, represented in Figure 4, the electric circuit and the base at which the
 253 springs set is attached has a motion characterised by $z(t)$.

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255 Fig. 4. Representation of a single degree-of-freedom system moving in a uniform and time-invariant
 256 magnetic field, in which an induced current in an equivalent RL circuit appears, and the base moves.

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258 The governing equation of the motion of the bar is given by

$$259 \quad m\ddot{u}(t) + k_0(u(t) - z(t)) = f_m(t), \quad (29)$$

260 where the magnetic force $f_m(t)$ is given again by Eq. (15), but in this case, the induced
 261 current is not given by (13), because the circuit has also the movement of the base. Instead,
 262 it is given by

$$263 \quad L \frac{di(t)}{dt} + Ri(t) = (\dot{u}(t) - \dot{z}(t)) B \ell. \quad (30)$$

264 Then, making use of the operational calculus as in the previous case, the resulting differential
 265 equation yields

$$266 \quad \frac{L}{R} m\ddot{u}(t) + m\ddot{u}(t) + \frac{L}{R} \left(k_0 + \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{L} \right) \dot{u}(t) + k_0 u(t) = \frac{L}{R} \left(k_0 + \frac{B^2 \ell^2}{L} \right) \dot{z}(t) + k_0 z(t), \quad (31)$$

267 which is equivalent to Eq. (8) of the mechanical model of Section 2.3, using again the
 268 assumptions of Eqs. (21)-(23).

269

270 **4. Validation**

271 The validation is carried out from two points of view, one analytical and the other
272 experimental. Firstly, the eddy currents force of Case 1 of the previous sections is compared
273 with the analytical results of the non-linear model published in [17]. Next, from the response
274 of the base motion of Case 2, a transmissibility function is obtained and compared with
275 experimental transmissibility measures carried out on an aluminium cantilever beam that
276 vibrates in a magnetic field, previously published by one of the authors in [18].

277

278 *4.1. Comparison with an analytical forced response*

279 Shi et al. [17] presented a non-linear model for the eddy currents damping forces based on a
280 viscous damping model in which damping force $f_{EC,NLV}(t)$ is non-linearly proportional to
281 velocity $\dot{u}(t)$,

$$282 \quad f_{EC,NLV}(t) = C(t)\dot{u}(t), \quad (32)$$

283 *i.e.*, the parameter $C(t)$ varies with time. For the particular case of a harmonic velocity given
284 by

$$285 \quad \dot{u}(t) = V_m \cos \omega t, \quad (33)$$

286 where V_m is the amplitude and ω is the angular frequency, the eddy currents force results
287 in [17].

$$288 \quad f_{EC,NLV}(t) = c_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + \frac{cV_m \cos(\omega t + \theta)}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2}}, \quad (34)$$

289 where c_1 is a constant with units of force, c is the equivalent viscous coefficient given by
290 Eq. (22), τ is the relaxation time given by Eq. (23), and the phase angle θ satisfies

$$291 \quad \tan \theta = -\omega \tau. \quad (35)$$

292

293 Next, let us get the eddy currents damping force $f_{EC,Z}(t)$ according to the model presented
294 in this paper based on the linear Zener model. This force is given by the magnetic force of
295 Eq. (15) but with a plus sign, and making use Eqs. (17) and (18), the Laplace transform of
296 this force gives

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$$F_{\text{EC,Z}}(s) = \frac{\dot{U}(s)B^2\ell^2}{Ls + R}, \quad (36)$$

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3 298 that, by means of Eqs. (22) and (23), it may be transformed into

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$$F_{\text{EC,Z}}(s) = c \frac{\dot{U}(s)}{s\tau + 1}. \quad (37)$$

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9 300 Taking into account Eq. (33), *i.e.* that the velocity is harmonic, the Laplace transform of the
10 301 force results in

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$$F_{\text{EC,Z}}(s) = cV_m \frac{s}{(s^2 + \omega^2)(s\tau + 1)}. \quad (38)$$

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16 303 To apply the inverse Laplace transform, this equation must be decomposed in partial
17 304 fractions as

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$$F_{\text{EC,Z}}(s) = cV_m \left(\frac{-1}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} \cdot \frac{\tau}{s\tau + 1} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2\tau^2}} \cdot \frac{s \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2\tau^2}} - \omega \frac{-\omega\tau}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2\tau^2}}}{s^2 + \omega^2} \right). \quad (39)$$

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25 306 The inverse Laplace transform this equation yields

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28 307
$$f_{\text{EC,Z}}(t) = \frac{-cV_m}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + \frac{cV_m}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2\tau^2}} \cos(\omega t + \theta). \quad (40)$$

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31 308 This equation for the eddy currents damping force obtained with the proposed model is
32 309 equivalent to the one of Shi et al. [17] given by Eq. (34), because Eq. (35) is satisfied and
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35 310 the constant c_1 should be

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$$c_1 = \frac{-cV_m}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2}, \quad (41)$$

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41 312 that actually depends on the angular frequency ω .

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45 314 *4.2. Comparison with experimental transmissibility measurements*

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47 315 In this Section the model is validated by the comparison with experimental results.
48 316 Specifically, the parameters of the transmissibility function obtained from Case 2 of the
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50 317 previous sections are obtained by curve fitting, using transmissibility experimental data. For
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52 318 that, let us consider a harmonic base motion given by

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55 319
$$z(t) = Z_0 e^{i\omega t}, \quad (42)$$

320 where Z_0 is the amplitude and ω is the angular frequency of the motion. Then, the
 321 displacement $u(t)$ is also harmonic with the same angular frequency and complex amplitude
 322 U_0 that can be solved from Eq. (8), transformed in

$$323 \quad \left[-i\omega^3\tau m - \omega^2 m + i\omega\tau(k_0 + k_1) + k_0 \right] U_0 = \left[i\omega\tau(k_0 + k_1) + k_0 \right] Z_0. \quad (43)$$

324 From this equation, the complex transmissibility function $T(\omega)$, defined as the ratio between
 325 U_0 and Z_0 , gives

$$326 \quad T(\omega) = \frac{i\omega\tau(k_0 + k_1) + k_0}{-i\omega^3\tau m - \omega^2 m + i\omega\tau(k_0 + k_1) + k_0}, \quad (44)$$

327 which can be transformed with non-dimensional parameters as

$$328 \quad T(r) = \frac{i(\beta + 2\zeta)r + 1}{-i\beta r^3 - r^2 + i(\beta + 2\zeta)r + 1}, \quad (45)$$

329 where $r = \omega / \omega_n$ is the normalised frequency, and ω_n , ζ and β are the natural frequency
 330 of the undamped system, the well-known viscous damping factor, and the non-viscous
 331 damping factor [21], given by

$$332 \quad \omega_n = \sqrt{k_0 / m}, \quad (46)$$

$$333 \quad \zeta = c / 2m\omega_n \quad (47)$$

334 and

$$335 \quad \beta = \tau\omega_n, \quad (48)$$

336 respectively. In the particular case in which the effect of the non-viscous damping factor β
 337 parameter is negligible with respect to the effect of the other terms, Eq. (45) becomes

$$338 \quad T(r) = \frac{i2\zeta r + 1}{-r^2 + i2\zeta r + 1}, \quad (49)$$

339 which corresponds to the transmissibility derived from the Kelvin-Voigt model. Therefore,
 340 it can be remarked that for the transmissibility function, the gain of the Zener model is more
 341 important as the parameter β is more significant, *i.e.* as the self-inductance plays a bigger
 342 role.

343 For the validation, next Eq. (45) is fitted to transmissibility experimental data and the
 344 parameters of the system are identified. The experimental data for the validation were
 345 published previously in [18]. Specifically, let us model the vibration due to the second mode

346 of a cantilever beam made of aluminium as a single DOF system. The second mode has been
 347 chosen as an example in this validation because its measurement quality. The geometrical
 348 properties of the beam are: vibrating length $\ell = 180$ mm, width $a = 9.93$ mm, and thickness
 349 $h = 0.404$ mm. The material properties are: electrical conductivity $\sigma = 3.77 \times 10^7$ S/m, and
 350 density $\rho = 2770$ kg/m³. Thus, the mass of the beam is $m_{\text{beam}} = 2.00 \times 10^{-3}$ kg. The mean value
 351 of the applied magnetic field intensity is $B_0 = 68.8 \times 10^{-3}$ T (see [18] for more details about
 352 the experimental measurements).

353 For the equivalent single degree-of-freedom system, the equivalent vibrating mass of
 354 the second mode of a cantilever beam is $m = 0.25 m_{\text{beam}}$ [22]. The natural frequency obtained
 355 in [18] is $f_n = 61.9$ Hz, or $\omega_n = 388.9$ rad/s. The rest of the parameters are obtained by the
 356 curve fitting of Eq. (45) by means of the minimization of the objective function

$$357 \quad g(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=k_{\min}}^{k_{\max}} |T_k - T(r_k)|, \quad (50)$$

358 where $k_{\min}$ and $k_{\max}$ denote the indexes of the minimum and maximum frequencies to
 359 adequately represent the second mode, T_k is the value of the complex experimental
 360 transmissibility at the normalised angular frequency r_k , and $\mathbf{x}$ is the unknown array
 361 conformed by the parameters β and ζ . These results derived of the curve fitting and the
 362 corresponding parameters of the Zener and the mechanical-electrical models are summarized
 363 in Table 1.

365 Table 1. Properties of the mechanical and mechanical-electrical models

Common properties				Mechanical model		Electrical model			
Experimental data		Curve fitting		Eqs. (46) & (48)		Eqs. (47) & (5)		Eqs. (21) & (22)	
m (g)	ω_n (rad/s)	β (-)	ζ (-)	k_0 (N/m)	τ (ms)	c (Ns/m)	k_1 (N/m)	L (μ H)	R (m Ω)
0.50	388.9	0.051	0.0055	75.6	0.013	0.021	16.3	7.83	59.7

366
 367 The result of the curve fitting procedure is shown in Figure 5, in which the Eq. (45) is
 368 compared with the experimental transmissibility curve [18].

369
370 Fig. 5. Transmissibility experimental data and fitted curve base on Zener model: (a) modulus and (b) phase.

371
372 It can be concluded that the fitted curve matches the experimental results both in modulus
373 and phase. The small differences may be due to the fact that the magnetic field is not uniform
374 throughout the beam. From an analysis of the theoretical curve, it can be pointed out that, in
375 this case, the resonance frequency is almost the same as the undamped natural frequency,
376 *i.e.*, 61.9 Hz, as was exhaustively studied in [18].

377 378 5. Parametric study

379 This Section presents a parametric study aimed at illustrating the influence of some
380 properties of the model on the frequency and time responses. Specifically, on the one hand
381 the influence of the magnitude of the magnetic field intensity on the frequency
382 transmissibility is studied. And on the other hand, an analysis is performed to reveal the
383 influence on the time response of the electrical properties L and R of the system, which are
384 related with the damping factors β and ζ .

386 5.1. Effect of the magnetic field intensity on frequency transmissibility

387 The transmissibility of the single-degree of freedom system given by Eq. (45) of Section 4
 388 is computed for three increasing different values of the magnetic field intensity B . The three
 389 studied cases are the following:

- 390 • Case 1: The magnetic field intensity is the reference value of the validation of
 391 Section 4.2, *i.e.* $B_1 = B_0 = 68.8 \times 10^{-3}$ T .
- 392 • Case 2: The magnetic field intensity is 1.5 times bigger than the reference value,
 393 $B_2 = 1.5B_0 = 103.2 \times 10^{-3}$ T .
- 394 • Case 3: The magnetic field intensity is 2 times bigger than the reference value,
 395 $B_3 = 2B_0 = 137.6 \times 10^{-3}$ T .

396 The curves obtained of the modulus and phase of the transmissibility as a function of the
 397 normalised frequency r are presented in Fig. 6 for the frequency range comprised between
 398 the 90% and the 110% of the natural frequency f_n .

399 Fig. 6. Transmissibility functions for three increasing magnetic field intensities: (a) modulus and (b) phase.
 400

401

402 This figure shows that the magnetic field intensity B is directly related with the vibration
 403 attenuation of the system: the bigger B , the higher the attenuation. In fact, B is related with
 404 the damping viscous coefficient c , as it was shown in Eq. (22). Specifically, by increasing
 405 the magnetic field intensity B by 1.5 and 2 times, the amplitude of the transmissibility
 406 resonance peak is reduced from 91.1 to 40.5 and to 22.8, respectively, *i.e.*, the amplitude is
 407 reduced by 55.5% and in 74.9%. These results show that in engineering applications, the
 408 damping capacity of a system may be controlled by the magnetic field intensity B .

410 5.2. Influence of the electrical properties on time response

411 In this Section the influence that the viscous damping factor ζ and the non-viscous damping
 412 factor β have on the time response of the system is studied. For that, the free vibration of a
 413 system that starts at rest and is subjected to an initial displacement u_0 is considered. In free
 414 vibration, Eq. (20) becomes

$$415 \quad \beta \ddot{u}(t) + \omega_n \dot{u}(t) + \omega_n^2 (\beta + 2\zeta) u(t) + \omega_n^3 u(t) = 0. \quad (51)$$

416 This equation may be solved by means of the Runge-Kutta method with the following initial
 417 conditions: $u_0 = 10^{-3} \text{ m}$, $\dot{u}_0 = 0$ and $\ddot{u}_0 = -\omega_n^2 u_0$ (the initial condition for the acceleration was
 418 proposed by [19]). To put in evidence the effect of the parameters β and ζ , three different
 419 cases are studied:

- 420 • Case 1: The electrical parameters L and R take the value of the reference case of the
 421 validation of Section 4.2, $L_1 = L_0 = 7.83 \mu\text{H}$ and $R_1 = R_0 = 5.97 \text{ m}\Omega$, *i.e.* the non-viscous
 422 damping factor and the viscous damping factor are also the same as the reference
 423 system, $\beta_1 = \beta_0 = 0.051$ and $\zeta_1 = \zeta_0 = 0.0055$.
- 424 • Case 2: Both the self-inductance and resistance parameters are reduced by 400 times,
 425 $L_2 = L_0 / 400 = 19.58 \text{ nH}$ and $R_2 = R_0 / 400 = 14.93 \mu\Omega$. Then, the non-viscous damping
 426 factor does not vary, $\beta_2 = \beta_0 = 0.051$, and the viscous damping factor is multiplied
 427 by 400, $\zeta_2 = 400\zeta_0 = 2.2$.
- 428 • Case 3: The resistance is the same as the Case 2, $R_3 = R_0 / 400 = 14.93 \mu\Omega$, but the
 429 self-inductance is reduced only 10 times, $L_3 = L_0 / 10 = 0.783 \mu\text{H}$. This implies that the
 430 viscous damping factor is the same as the Case 2, $\zeta_3 = 400\zeta_0 = 2.2$, but the non-
 431 viscous damping factor is multiplied by 40, $\beta_3 = 40\beta_0 = 2.04$.

432 The numerical values of these study cases are chosen to reveal different behaviour that the
 433 Zener model is able to reproduce and the viscous one is not. The response of the system is
 434 computed at the time corresponding 5 times the natural period of the system, $t_{\max} = 5T_n = 5/f_n$
 435 . The normalised response $u(t)/u_0$ of the three study cases are represented in Fig. 7 as a
 436 function of the normalised time t/T_n .

437
 438 Fig. 7. Time response of the system for three different pairs of L and R , corresponding to three different pairs
 439 of damping factors β and ζ .

440
 441 To analyse these curves, it is important to take into account some properties of the Zener
 442 model that differentiate it from the Kelvin-Voigt model. The behaviour of the Kelvin-Voigt
 443 model may be underdamped, critically damped or overdamped depending of the value of the
 444 viscous damping factor ζ compared with the critical value that is equal to 1. However, the
 445 Zener model has two different critical damping factors, namely the critical viscous damping
 446 factor $\zeta_{cr} = 4/3\sqrt{3}$ and the critical non-viscous damping factor $\beta_{cr} = 1/3\sqrt{3}$. A deep study
 447 of the behaviour of the Zener model depending of the values of the damping factors is carried
 448 out by Adhikari in [21].

449 Next, the following conclusions are derived from Fig. 7:

- 450 • Case 1 presents a lightly damped vibratory behaviour, in which the normalised
 451 amplitude is reduced from 1 to 0.84 in 5 periods. This corresponds to an
 452 underdamped system, because the viscous damping factor is smaller than the critical
 453 value $\zeta < \zeta_{cr}$.

- 454 • On the contrary, Case 2 does not show vibration, *i.e.* it is an overdamped system.
 455 This is because the viscous damping factor is bigger than the critical value $\zeta > \zeta_{cr}$
 456 and the non-viscous damping factor is smaller than the corresponding critical value
 457 $\beta < \beta_{cr}$.
- 458 • However, Case 3 corresponds to a particular case of the Zener model that can not be
 459 reproduced by the Kelvin-Voigt model. In Case 3, the system vibrates but the
 460 oscillatory behaviour does not cross the zero value, *i.e.*, the vibrations happen around
 461 a variable equilibrium position governed by the non-viscous mode (see *e.g.* Ref. [19]
 462 for details about the modes of the Zener model). This is because the viscous damping
 463 factor is bigger than the critical value $\zeta > \zeta_{cr}$ like in Case 2, but the non-viscous
 464 damping factor is bigger than the critical value $\beta > \beta_{cr}$.

465 Concluding, in this section it has been shown that the electrical properties of the system have
 466 influence on the mechanical behaviour of the system when it is subjected to a magnetic field
 467 and eddy currents appear. This influence can be studied by means of the equivalent
 468 viscoelastic Zener model trough the damping factors related with the electrical properties.

469 6. Conclusions

470 In this paper the eddy currents damping appearing in a metallic object moving in a uniform
 471 magnetic field has been explained as Zener viscoelastic damping, namely, the effect of the
 472 eddy currents damping is equivalent to that of viscoelasticity.
 473

474 To find this equivalence, the eddy currents have been modelled by a coupled
 475 mechanical-electrical system for two different excitations, a harmonic force and a base
 476 motion. It has been found that the governing equations of the coupled system contains terms
 477 of derivatives of the displacement up to the third order, the same as in a viscoelastic system
 478 modelled with a Zener model. In viscoelasticity, the third order derivative term is related
 479 with relaxation, one of the main properties of viscoelasticity. It has been found that, in the
 480 case of the eddy currents damping, the relaxation is provided by the self-inductance of the
 481 object. The relaxation implies forces proportional to the jerk, which explains some
 482 experimental results [16]. In addition, the Zener model is a linear model that has been widely
 483 studied in the literature, as opposed to non-linear models proposed by other authors to
 484 explain similar properties as the forces proportional to the third derivative of the
 485 displacement [17,23]. These other non-linear models are based on the Kelvin-Voigt model
 486 in which the viscous damping coefficient c is not a constant and the system is no longer

1
2 487 linear. However, by means of the Zener model, the well-known properties of the linear
3 488 viscoelasticity can be directly extrapolated to the systems with eddy currents damping.

4 489 The validation of the analogy has been carried out in two different ways. On the one
5 490 hand, an analytical validation that consists in the comparison of the forced response with a
6 491 model of the literature. On the other hand, the validation comes from the experimental
7 492 transmissibility data of an aluminium cantilever beam vibrating in a magnetic field.

8
9 493 A parametric study has been presented to reveal the influence that the magnetic field
10 494 intensity and the electrical properties of the system has on its mechanical response.
11 495 Specifically, it has been studied the influence of the magnetic field intensity on the frequency
12 496 response and the influence of the electrical properties on the time response. In this manner,
13 497 it has been revealed how the magnetic field intensity influences on the attenuation of the
14 498 system. Also, it has been shown that the system has vibratory behaviour or not depending
15 499 on the magnitude of electrical properties of the system.

16 500 Concluding, this paper shows that for practical engineering applications as the design
17 501 of eddy currents dampers, the utilisation of the properties of the well-known Zener model,
18 502 could help designers to improve the effectiveness of their designs.

19 503

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23 507

24 508 **References**

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